

AN EFFICIENT HEURISTIC ALGORITHM FOR FLEXIBLE JOB SHOP SCHEDULING WITH MAINTENANCE CONSTRAINTS

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Abstract

This paper deals with the flexible job shop scheduling problem with the preventive maintenance constraints where the objectives are to minimize the overall completion time (makespan), the total workload of machines and the workload of the most loaded machine. A fast heuristic algorithm based on a constructive procedure is developed to solve the problem in very short time. The algorithm is tested on the benchmark instances from the literature in order to evaluate its performance. Computational results show that, the proposed heuristic method is computationally efficient and promising for practical problems.

Keywords

Scheduling, Multi-Objective Flexible Job Shop, Preventive Maintenance, Heuristic, Local Search.

1. Introduction

The job shop scheduling problem (JSP) is one of the most popular scheduling problems and has attracted many researchers due to both its practical importance and its complexity [1]. In the $n \times m$ classical JSP, a set of n jobs have to be processed on a group of m machines, where the processing of each job i consists of J_i operations performed on these machines. Each job has a processing order on the machines which is fixed and known in advance, i.e., each operation has to be performed on a given machine. The processing times of all operations are also fixed and known. Each machine can process at most one operation at a time, and the operations are processed on the machines without interruption [2,3]. A typical performance indicator for the JSP is the makespan, i.e., the time needed to complete all the jobs.

The flexible job shop scheduling problem (FJSP) is a generalization of the classical JSP, in which each operation is allowed to be processed by any among set of candidate machines, instead of a given machine; and thus, the scheduling problem is to choose for each operation, a machine and a starting time at which the operation must be processed. The FJSP is more difficult than the classical JSP because it contains an additional problem which is to determine the job routes, or to assign the operations to the machines. This problem is known to be strongly NP-hard even if each job has at most three operations and there are two machines [4].

The FJSP with PM constraints is to assign each operation to an appropriate machine out of a set

of machines capable of executing it, and to sequence the job operations and PM operations on each machine, in order to minimize one or more criteria. This paper presents a solution method to solve this problem in order to minimize the following three objectives:

- (1) The maximum completion time of the machines, i.e. the makespan (C_{max}).
- (2) The total workload of the machines, which represents the total working time of all machines (W_T). This objective is of interest if machines differ with respect to the efficiency.
- (3) The maximal machine workload, i.e., the maximum working time spent on any machine (W_{max}). This objective is used to prevent assignment of too much work to a single machine and to keep the balance of work distribution over the machines.

In this article, the weighted sum of the above three objectives is taken as the objective function. This approach, i.e. the weighted sum, in dealing with the multi-objective optimization, is easy for decision makers to understand, convenient for developers to implement, and available to modify the weights for satisfying the requirements of decision makers. In this study, the PM periods are also included in the above three criteria, since the PM periods are mandatory and the scheduler has to schedule them along with the jobs to be processed. The objective function of the studied problem is therefore computed as (1):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize } Obj &= W_1 \times C_{max} + W_2 \times W_T + W_3 \times W_{max} \\ \text{such that: } & W_1 + W_2 + W_3 = 1; \quad W_1, W_2, W_3 \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

W_1 , W_2 , and W_3 represent the weight coefficients of the three objectives.

The FJSP with PM constraints is strongly NP-hard, since the problem without PM scheduling is already strongly NP-hard [4]. Therefore, as it can be seen in the literature review section, approximate algorithms, mainly metaheuristics, have been used to solve the problem.

In this study, a simple and easily extendable heuristic algorithm based on a constructive procedure is presented to solve the FJSP with PM constraints (section 3). The main purpose is to produce reasonable and applicable schedules very quickly. It can also be used to improve the quality of the initial feasible solution of metaheuristics applied to solve the problem, since the choice of a good initial solution is an important aspect of the performance of algorithms in terms of computing time and solution quality [5,6,7]. In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed heuristic, it is implemented using several benchmark problems and the results of the computational experiments are presented (section 4). The results show that our novel method can obtain good solutions in very short time. Concluding remarks are given in the last section.

Assumptions considered in this paper are as follows:

- (1) There is only one PM operation on each machine during the planning horizon. Each PM operation has to be performed within a predefined time window, and its duration is determined in advance.
- (2) Jobs are independent of each other.
- (3) Machines are independent of each other.
- (4) Setup and transportation times are negligible.
- (5) Preemption is not allowed, i.e. a started operation (either operation of a job or a PM operation) can not be interrupted during its processing.
- (6) Each machine can process at most one operation (either job operation or PM operation) at the same time.
- (7) An operation can not be performed by more than one machine at the same time.
- (8) All jobs have equal priorities.

- (9) Machines never break down and are available throughout the scheduling period.
- (10) All jobs are available at time zero.

The notations used throughout the paper are as follows:

n : number of jobs,

m : number of machines,

i, z : index of jobs; $i, z = 1, \dots, n$,

J_i : number of operations of job i ,

$\max J$: maximum number of operations per job (i.e., $\max J = \max_i J_i$),

j : index of operations; $j = 1, \dots, J_i$,

k, y : index of machines; $k, y = 1, \dots, m$,

t_{ijy} : processing time of operation j of job i on machine y ,

C_{ij} : completion time of operation j of job i ,

W_T : total workload of machines (the workload of each machine is defined by the sum of processing times of all operations assigned to it),

W_{max} : critical machine workload, i.e. the workload of the most loaded machine,

dur_y : duration of the preventive maintenance task of machine y ,

(tE_y, tL_y) : time window associated with the PM task on machine y , where tE_y is the earliest possible completion time, and tL_y is the latest possible completion time.

2.Literature Review

The vast majority of papers dealing with scheduling problems assume that the machines are continuously available for processing during the whole planning horizon. However, this assumption may not be true in real industrial settings, since the machines may become unavailable during the planning period for many reasons such as unforeseen breakdowns (stochastic unavailability [8]), or due to the use of the equipments for planned activities such as preventive maintenance (PM) tasks that conflict with scheduling decisions (i.e. deterministic unavailability, in which the periods of unavailability are known in advance).

Recently, many researchers began to study the scheduling problems with PM constraints, because PM is considered as a common reason for machine unavailability. PM is used by manufacturing industries for following reasons: PM can reduce the probability of unforeseen breakdowns; in manufacturing systems that use PM, if a machine breaks down, then its unavailability time interval is expected to be significantly reduced; and therefore PM can restore the reliability of machines and improve the machine utilization ratio. This paper deals with the FJSP with PM constraints and assumes that the starting time of PM operations is not known in advance and must be determined during the production scheduling process. However, each PM operation has to be executed within a given time window. These constraints are referred to as non-fixed availability constraints in the literature. In fixed availability constraints, each PM operation is started at a fixed time point which is predetermined by maintenance planning system. We also suppose that there is only one PM operation on each machine during the planning horizon. This assumption brings the problem closer to the real manufacturing situations [9].

Scheduling problems under the machine availability constraints have recently been investigated in numerous papers. Schmidt [10] presents a survey of existing methods for solving deterministic scheduling problems with availability constraints, as well as complexity results; and most recent survey of scheduling with deterministic machine availability constraints can be seen in reference

[11]. However, for the FJSP, there are only a few papers that deal with the FJSP under resource constraints. Dalfard and Mohammadi [12] propose two metaheuristics (a hybrid genetic algorithm and a simulated annealing algorithm) for the multi-objective FJSP with parallel machines, maintenance costs, jobs due dates and jobs release times to minimize the mean tardiness, the makespan and the mean flowtime. As there is no similar work in the literature, they compare the solutions of these metaheuristic methods with those obtained by solving a mathematical model using the software LINGO. Gao et al. [9] consider the FJSP with non-fixed availability constraints where each machine is subject to an arbitrary number of PM tasks, and present a hybrid genetic algorithm (hGA) to solve the problem with a multiobjective function including makespan, total machine workload and the workload of the most loaded machine. Chan et al. [13] develop a heuristic based on genetic algorithm (GA), namely iterative GA (IGA), for solving the bicriteria FJSP under resource constraints. The objectives considered are the minimization of makespan and machine idle cost. Zribi et al. [14] investigate the multi-purpose machine (MPM) job shop scheduling problem with fixed machine availability constraints, and apply a GA to solve the problem. Rajkumar et al. [15] present a greedy randomized adaptive search procedure (GRASP) to solve the FJSP under non-fixed availability constraints and with the same objectives as those considered by Gao et al. [9]. Moradi et al. [16] solve the FJSP with PM under two objectives: the minimization of makespan for the production part and the minimization of system unavailability for the maintenance part. Vilcot and Billaut [17] study a general job shop scheduling problem with multiple constraints, coming from printing and boarding industry. They present an algorithm based on tabu search and GA for minimizing the makespan and the maximum lateness. Chan et al. [18] consider the distributed flexible manufacturing system (FMS) scheduling problem subject to machine maintenance constraints, in which the maintenance time is related to the machine age. The presented method also covers the FJSP with maintenance activities. Wang and Yu [19] present a heuristic based on the filtered beam search (FBS) algorithm to solve the FJSP with the non-fixed and fixed machine availability constraints due to the PM.

3. Proposed Heuristic Approach

In this section, we present a heuristic method to solve the problem. This approach is motivated by the idea of developing a constructive heuristic that considers simultaneously several factors affecting the solution quality and intelligently balances their effects in the process of schedule generation, and the observation that it could lead to good results in some preliminary computational experiments on a wide range of difficult scheduling problems. This algorithm has a simple structure, is easy to implement, and requires very little computational effort which makes it preferable over other more complex and time-consuming approaches. Some notations that will be used in the algorithm are defined as follows:

A_{ij} : set of machines which are capable to execute operation j of job i ,

N_{ij} : number of members of the set A_{ij} ,

s_{ij} : mean processing time of operation j of job i over the machines belonging to the set A_{ij}

(i.e., $s'_{ij} = (\sum_{y \in A_{ij}} t_{ijy}) / N_{ij}$),

sj_i : total mean processing time of job i (i.e., $sj_i = \sum_{j=1}^{J_i} s'_{ij}$),

sk_y : total weighted processing time on machine y which is calculated as: sk_y

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ \text{if } y \in A_{ij}}}^{J_i} \frac{S'_{ij}}{N_{ij}},$$

M : a large number.

An outline of the proposed heuristic algorithm is given in Fig. 1 and the pseudocode of the algorithm is shown in Fig. 2. Some other notations used in these two figures will be defined later.

```

until all operations of all jobs are scheduled, repeat
{
    • For all  $i, j, k$  (such that: 1.  $j \leq J_i$ , 2.  $j=1$  or  $(j-1)$ th operation of job  $i$  is already scheduled, and 3.  $j$ th operation of job  $i$  is an unscheduled operation and machine  $k$  is capable of processing this operation), calculate the value of  $TC$ .
    • For all unscheduled PM operations, calculate the value of  $TC$ .
    • Select the operation (either job operation or PM operation) with minimum  $TC$  and schedule it on the last position of current partial sequence on the corresponding machine.
}
    
```

Fig. 1. General outline of the proposed heuristic algorithm

Initialization:

- Sort the jobs in increasing order of their sj_i and call the resulting set: i_sort . Let i_sort_z be z th job of the list i_sort .
- Sort the machines in increasing order of their sk_y and call the resulting set: k_sort . Let k_sort_y be y th machine of the list k_sort .

Constructive Algorithm:

```

for  $x_1 := L_{x_1}$  to  $U_{x_1}$  do
for  $x_2 := L_{x_2}$  to  $U_{x_2}$  do
  :
for  $x_6 := L_{x_6}$  to  $U_{x_6}$  do
for  $x_7 := 0$  to 1 do
{
    % Beginning of a schedule generation

    until all job operations and all PM operations are
    scheduled, repeat the following steps:
    {
        for  $j := 1$  to  $maxJ$  do
        {
            Set  $TC^* := M$ 
        }
    }
}
    
```

```

for i':=1 to n do
{
  Set i:=x7.(i_sorti')+(1-x7).(i_sort(n-i'+1)),
  Set b:=0,

  if ( 1. j ∈ Ji, and
        2. j=1 or (j-1)th operation of job i
          is already scheduled, and
        3. jth operation of job i is an
          unscheduled operation) then
  {
    for k':=1 to m do
    {
      Set k:= k_sort(m-k'+1),

      if (machine k is capable of
          processing jth operation of job
          i) then
      {
        if ( 1. PM of machine
              k is already
              scheduled; or
              2. PM task of machine
              k is not already
              scheduled, and: Cij ≤ tLk -
              durk, (such that,
              Cij=max (Cmaxk, Ci,j-
              1)+tijk )
              ) then
        {
          Set TC:= ∑r=15 wr.xr.Cr,
          if TC<TC* then
          {
            Set TC*:= TC
            Set z:=i
            Set y:=k
            Set b:=0
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }

  if ( PM operation of machine k is an unscheduled operation) then
  {
    Set TC:= x6. { ∑r=15 wr.xr.Cr }
    if TC<TC* then
    {
      Set TC*:= TC
    }
  }
}

```


$$C_1 = \max (Cmax_y, C_{i,j-1}) + t_{ijy} \quad (4)$$

$$C_2 = \max (0, (C_{i,j-1} - Cmax_y)) \quad (5)$$

$$C_3 = t_{ijy} \quad (6)$$

$$C_4 = w_T + t_{ijy} \quad (7)$$

$$C_5 = w_y + t_{ijy} \quad (8)$$

$$C_1 = \max (Cmax_y + dur_y, tE_y) \quad (9)$$

$$C_2 = \max (0, (tE_y - dur_y - Cmax_y)) \quad (10)$$

$$C_3 = dur_y \quad (11)$$

$$C_4 = w_T + dur_y \quad (12)$$

$$C_5 = w_y + dur_y \quad (13)$$

TC is weighted sum of some criteria which are established based on the factors affecting the objective function value. Minimization of TC in the process of schedule generation leads to improvement in solution quality. w_r ($r=1,2,\dots,5$) are constants and x_r ($r=1,2,\dots,6$) are integer variables used to increase the flexibility and effectiveness of criterion TC and have a significant impact on the performance of the algorithm. The constant weights (w_r) are preliminary estimated weights assigned to criteria according to their importance, and the coefficients x_r are variables bounded in a given range and used to refine the TC . $Cmax_y$ is the maximum completion time across all the operations scheduled on machine y ; i.e., the completion time of last operation (either job operation or PM operation) scheduled on machine y . w_T is the total workload of machines for the partial schedule. w_y is the workload of machine y for the partial schedule. C_1 and C_1 are applied to decrease $Cmax_y$; C_2 and C_2 are used to decrease idle times; clearly, both these objectives ($Cmax_y$ and idle times) affect the main objective function, i.e. $Cmax$. The values of other objective functions, i.e. W_T and $Wmax$, are directly affected by (C_4 and C_4) and (C_5 and C_5), respectively. For assigning operations to a machine, their processing time are also taken into account by C_3 and C_3 .

Other notations used in the pseudocode of the proposed heuristic are as follows:

TC^* : denotes the best value of TC . After each operation is scheduled, TC^* is reset to M .

L_x ($r=1,2,\dots,6$): lower limit of x_r .

U_x ($r=1,2,\dots,6$): upper limit of x_r .

b : a binary variable taking value 1 if PM task of a machine is selected for scheduling, and 0 if an operation of a job is selected for scheduling.

As it can be seen in Fig. 2, the algorithm first sorts the jobs in increasing (decreasing) order of their sj_i and then uses this order for evaluating their operations. Therefore, if two unscheduled operations belonging to two different jobs have the same value of TC , then according to this sorting of the jobs, the operation of job with smaller (greater) sj_i is selected for scheduling sooner than the other operation. Binary variable x_7 is applied for setting the order of the sorting (i.e. either increasing order or decreasing order), it takes a value of 1 for increasing order and 0 for decreasing one. Similarly, the algorithm first sorts the machines in decreasing order of their sk_y and then uses this order to evaluate assigning the operations to each of them. In our preliminary computational experiments, we used these sortings of the jobs and machines instead of randomly selecting them, and interestingly observed that these sortings can lead to better solutions. Specially, the results showed that in most cases, the sorting of the machines in decreasing order of their sk_y leads to better solutions in comparison with increasing order. It is because the machines with larger sk_y which are firstly selected for scheduling have more sensibility and effect on the objective value. In other words, the schedule of these machines determines the performance of overall schedule of the problem. Therefore, we have used only decreasing order of them in the computational experiments. x_r^* ($r=1,2,\dots,7$) are the best values of variables x_r (i.e. the values

corresponding to the best solutions). Indeed, for various values of x_r ($r=1,2,\dots,7$), the algorithm of Fig. 1 is run and a complete schedule is generated. Among all these schedules, the one with minimum Obj is reported as the final solution. The values of variables x_r for this best solution are also reported and denoted by x_r^* (see Table 2). This best schedule obtained from the heuristic is next improved by a shift neighborhood based local search procedure. The pseudocode of this local search is shown in Appendix.

As mentioned earlier, the evaluation of the operations for scheduling them is done using the criterion TC , i.e. the unscheduled operation with minimum TC is selected for scheduling.

4. Computational Results

This section describes the computational experiments conducted in order to evaluate the performance of the proposed heuristic method. First, some preliminary experiments have been conducted for the parameter settings. Regarding the test on various values for the parameters of the algorithm and considering the computational results, we used the settings of Table 1 for benchmarking the presented algorithm.

Table 1. Parameter settings for the heuristic

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
L_{x_1}	0	U_{x_1}	2	w_1	1
L_{x_2}	0	U_{x_2}	2	w_2	1
L_{x_3}	0	U_{x_3}	2	w_3	1
L_{x_4}	0	U_{x_4}	2	w_4	0.5
L_{x_5}	0	U_{x_5}	2	w_5	0.2
L_{x_6}	0	U_{x_6}	2		

The algorithm was coded in C language and run on a Pentium IV, 2.2 GHz and 2.0 GB RAM PC. The benchmark problems used were the set of 4 instances presented by Kacem et al. [20,21,22] and extended by Gao et al. [9] and Rajkumar et al. [15] to problems involving maintenance constraints. All these instances have exactly one PM activity on each machine in the planning horizon. Table 2 shows a comparison of the results of our algorithm with those of two recently published algorithms: the hybrid genetic algorithm (hGA) presented by Gao et al. [9] and the greedy randomized adaptive search procedure (GRASP) developed by Rajkumar et al. [15]. The results are obtained under two objective functions: $Obj1=0.3 \times C_{max} + 0.5 \times W_T + 0.2 \times W_{max}$, and $Obj2=0.2 \times C_{max} + 0.5 \times W_T + 0.3 \times W_{max}$. *Weights* denotes the weights of the objectives. *Name* and *Size* refer to the name of each instance and its size in terms of the number of jobs, machines and operations, respectively. C_{max} , W_T and W_{max} stand for the makespan, total workload and maximum workload, respectively. *RPD* is the relative percentage deviation and calculated as (14):

$$RPD = \frac{Obj_{alg} - Obj^*}{Obj^*} \times 100, \tag{14}$$

where Obj_{alg} is the objective function (Obj) value generated by the algorithm and Obj^* is the best value of Obj obtained from the three algorithms. *Sol.1* and *Sol.2* show the results obtained by the heuristic algorithm and local search procedure, respectively. *Time(s)* indicates the computational time to solve each instance by the heuristic (including the time spent on the local search) in seconds. The best values of variables x_r (i.e. x_r^*), $r=1,2,\dots,7$; are also reported in Table 2. Symbol

‘-’ denotes that the result was not presented in the given reference. As it can be seen in the table, for the results corresponding to *Obj2*, i.e. cases with larger weights for W_{max} , the value of x_7 is equal to 0.25, i.e. near to zero. It means that the sorting of the jobs in decreasing order of their s_j leads to better solutions in comparison with increasing order. It is because the jobs with larger s_j which are firstly selected for scheduling have more impact on W_{max} . The results of Table 2 also show that the value of x_6 is equal to zero in almost all instances, meaning that TC for PM operations is set to zero, i.e. PM operations are started at earliest possible time. This intuitively gives more opportunities to job operations to be inserted in good positions of the overall schedule. The average value of each variable $x_r, r=1,2,\dots,5$ can be considered as the relative effect of the corresponding criterion on the quality of solutions. Of course, as it can be seen in the table, the values of each variable $x_r, r=1,2,\dots,5$ have relatively high variance, meaning that they are strongly dependent on the specifications of problem instance under consideration and on the values of other variables x_r . The proposed algorithm selects for each instance, best combination of x_r values leading to best result.

In Table 2, an interesting observation is that the proposed heuristic is better than the other two metaheuristic algorithms in terms of the average RPD, considering that it is very fast and needs only 0.5 sec. on average. Figures 3 and 4 show a graphical comparison of the RPD of the three methods for *Obj1* and *Obj2*, respectively.

Table 2. Computational results for benchmark instances

		Heuristic																	
		Sol.1							Sol.2										
Weights	Name	Size	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj1	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj1	RPD	Time(s)
w1=0.3 w2=0.5 w3=0.2	4-5-nfa	4,5,12	15	40	9	26.3	1	1	1	2	1	0	0	13	40	9	25.7	0	0.05
	8-8-nfa	8,8,27	31	103	16	64	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	20	103	16	60.7	0.998	0.22
	10-10-nfa	10,10,30	11	60	8	34.9	2	1	1	0	2	0	1	9	60	8	34.3	0.587	0.38
	15-10-nfa	15,10,56	20	108	13	62.6	2	1	2	0	1	1	1	15	104	14	59.3	0	1.45
	Average						1.25	0.75	1	0.75	1.25	0.25	0.5					0.396	0.52
Weights	Name	Size	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj2	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj2	RPD	Time(s)
w1=0.2 w2=0.5 w3=0.3	4-5-nfa	4,5,12	15	40	9	25.7	1	1	1	2	1	0	0	13	40	9	25.3	0	0.05
	8-8-nfa	8,8,27	31	103	16	62.5	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	20	103	16	60.3	0.668	0.22
	10-10-nfa	10,10,30	11	60	8	34.6	2	1	1	0	2	0	1	9	60	8	34.2	0.885	0.36
	15-10-nfa	15,10,56	27	104	14	61.6	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	14	105	12	58.9	0	1.09
	Average						0.75	0.5	0.5	1.25	1.5	0	0.25					0.388	0.43
		hGA							GRASP										
Weights	Name	Size	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj1	RPD	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj1	RPD							
w1=0.3 w2=0.5 w3=0.2	4-5-nfa	4,5,12	-	-	-	-	-	16	40	9	26.6	3.502							
	8-8-nfa	8,8,27	17	105	15	60.6	0.832	18	103	16	60.1	0							
	10-10-nfa	10,10,30	8	61	7	34.3	0.587	9	60	7	34.1	0							
	15-10-nfa	15,10,56	12	109	12	60.5	2.024	16	107	13	60.9	2.698							
	Average						1.147					1.55							
Weights	Name	Size	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj2	RPD	Cmax	Wt	Wmax	Obj2	RPD							
w1=0.2 w2=0.5 w3=0.3	4-5-nfa	4,5,12	-	-	-	-	-	16	40	9	25.9	2.372							
	8-8-nfa	8,8,27	17	105	15	60.4	0.835	18	103	16	59.9	0							
	10-10-nfa	10,10,30	8	61	7	34.2	0.885	9	60	7	33.9	0							
	15-10-nfa	15,10,56	12	109	12	60.5	2.716	16	107	13	60.3	2.377							
	Average						1.479					1.187							

Fig. 3 Comparison of the three methods for *Obj1* (i.e. $W_1=0.3, W_2=0.5, W_3=0.2$)

Fig. 4 Comparison of the three methods for *Obj2* (i.e. $W_1=0.2, W_2=0.5, W_3=0.3$)

5. Conclusion

This paper investigates the flexible job shop scheduling problem with preventive maintenance constraints. The objective is to minimize the makespan, the total workload of machines and the workload of most loaded machine. The main purpose is to produce reasonable schedules very quickly. A simple and easily extendable heuristic based on a constructive procedure is presented. The proposed approach uses an accurate, relatively comprehensive and flexible criterion for scheduling job operations and PM operations and constructing a feasible high-quality solution. In this criterion, several factors affecting the quality of solutions are used and to each of these factors, a variable weight is assigned. By setting different values to these variable weights, different solutions are generated and evaluated. The algorithm is tested on benchmark instances from the literature in order to evaluate its performance. The computational results show that the proposed approach can yield very good solutions with very little computational time. Since the presented method is a heuristic, its results cannot be compared in a meaningful way with those of the methods evaluated as they are metaheuristic based algorithms. However, the computational results show that the proposed heuristic outperforms the other metaheuristic methods evaluated,

in terms of both the average RPD and the computational time. Further research needs to be conducted in applying other criteria in the TC in order to improve the solution quality and to adapt the approach to other objectives and process constraints.

Appendix. Shift neighborhood based local search procedure(l and l' are indices of position in the machine path. L, L' denote the number of operations assigned to machines y and y' in the current solution, respectively.)

```
Repeat:
  for  $y:=1$  to  $m$  do
    for  $l:=1$  to  $L$  do
      for  $y':=1$  to  $m$  do
        for  $l':=1$  to  $L'$  do
          if ( $y \neq y'$  or ( $y=y'$  and  $l' < l$ )) then
            {
              • Remove the operation placed in position  $l$ 
                on machine  $y$  and insert it into position  $l'$ 
                on machine  $y'$ , leaving all other relative
                operation orders unchanged.
              • If the objective value of the obtained
                sequence ( $Obj$ ) is less than the best
                objective value obtained so far ( $Obj^*$ ), then
                set  $Obj^*:=Obj$ ; Otherwise, insert the
                operation into its previous position.
            }
        until (no improvement occurs over the best solution)
```

References

- [1] Jain, A.S., Meeran, S., Deterministic job-shop scheduling: Past, present and future, *European Journal of Operational Research* 113 (2) (1998) 390–434.
- [2] Baker, K., *Introduction to sequencing and scheduling*, New York: Wiley (1974).
- [3] Pinedo, M., *Scheduling: theory, algorithms and systems*, Englewood cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall (2002).
- [4] Garey, M.R., Johnson, D.S., Sethi, R., The complexity of flow shop and job-shop scheduling, *Mathematics of Operations Research* 1 (2) (1976) 117–129.
- [5] Dell'Amico, M., Trubian, M., Applying tabu-search to the job-shop scheduling problem, *Annals of Operations Research* 4 (1993) 231–252.
- [6] Matsuo, H., Suh, C., Sullivan, R., A controlled search simulated annealing method for the general job-shop scheduling problem, Tech. Rep. 03-04-88, Dept. of Management, The University of Texas, Austin (1988).
- [7] Van Laarhoven, P., Aarts, E., Lenstra, J., Job shop scheduling by simulated annealing, *Operations Research* 40 (1992) 113–125.
- [8] Xiong, J., Xing, L.-N., Chen, Y.-W., Robust scheduling for multi-objective flexible job-shop problems with random machine breakdowns, *International Journal of Production Economics* 141 (2013) 112–126.
- [9] Gao, J., Gen, M., Sun, L., Scheduling jobs and maintenances in flexible job shop with a hybrid genetic algorithm, *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 17 (2006) 493–507.
- [10] Schmidt, G., Scheduling with limited machine availability, *European Journal of Operational Research* 121 (1) (2000) 1–15.
- [11] Ma, Y., Chu, C., Zuo, C., A survey of scheduling with deterministic machine availability constraints, *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 58 (2010) 199–211.
- [12] Dalfard, V. M., Mohammadi, G., Two meta-heuristic algorithms for solving multi-objective flexible job-shop scheduling with parallel machine and maintenance constraints, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* 64 (6) (2012) 2111–2117.

- [13] Chan, F.T.S., Wong, T.C., Chan, L.Y., Flexible job-shop scheduling problem under resource constraints *International Journal of Production Research* 44 (11) (2006) 2071–2089.
- [14] Zribi, N., Kamel, A.E., Borne, P., Minimizing the makespan for the MPM job-shop with availability constraints, *International Journal of Production Economics* 112 (1) (2008) 151–160.
- [15] Rajkumar, M., Asokan, P., Vamsikrishna, V., A GRASP algorithm for flexible job-shop scheduling with maintenance constraints, *International Journal of Production Research* 48 (22) (2010) 6821–6836.
- [16] Moradi, E., Ghomi, S.M.T.F., Zandieh, M., Bi-objective optimization research on integrated fixed time interval preventive maintenance and production for scheduling flexible job-shop problem, *Expert Systems with Applications* 38 (6) (2011) 7169–7178.
- [17] Vilcot, G., Billaut, J.-C., A tabu search and a genetic algorithm for solving a bicriteria general job shop scheduling problem, *European Journal of Operational Research* 190 (2) (2008) 398–411.
- [18] Chan, F.T.S., Chung, S.H., Chan, L.Y., Finke, G., Tiwari, M.K., Solving distributed FMS scheduling problems subject to maintenance: Genetic algorithms approach, *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* 22 (5-6) (2006) 493–504.
- [19] Wang, S., Yu, J., An effective heuristic for flexible job-shop scheduling problem with maintenance activities, *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 59 (2010) 436–447.
- [20] Kacem, I., Hammadi, S., Borne, P., Approach by localization and multiobjective evolutionary optimization for flexible job-shop scheduling problems, *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C*, 32(1) (2002) 1–13.
- [21] Kacem, I., Hammadi, S., Borne, P., Pareto-optimality approach for flexible job-shop scheduling problems: hybridization of evolutionary algorithms and fuzzy logic, *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation* 60 (2002) 245–276.
- [22] Xia, W., Wu, Z., An effective hybrid optimization approach for multi-objective flexible job-shop scheduling problems, *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 48 (2005) 409–425.